

Thermal Decomposition of Potassium Perchlorate-Chromium(III) Chloride and Potassium Chlorate-Chromium(III) Chloride Mixtures.

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The thermal decomposition of potassium perchlorate and potassium chlorate in presence of chromium(III) chloride hexahydrate was studied by thermogravimetry and differential thermal analysis. The decomposition products were examined by chemical analysis, infrared spectral measurements and X-ray powder patterns. Cr(III) is found to get oxidized completely into Cr(VI) when KClO_4 and KClO_3 contents are greater than two and three moles respectively per mole of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. A part of Cr(III) is converted into CrO_2Cl_2 , with the major amount in the form of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. The formation of CrO_2Cl_2 decreases with the increase the concentrations of the oxidants.

PERCHLORATES and chlorates are known for their high oxygen contents and as such are the powerful oxidizing agents¹. The alkali metal perchlorates and chlorates on thermolysis, decompose to the metal chlorides and oxygen. Recently we have made detailed investigations on the thermal decomposition^{3,4} of KClO_4 and KClO_3 in presence of Cr_2O_3 and it is observed that Cr_2O_3 not only lowers the decomposition temperatures of pure KClO_4 and KClO_3 but also gets oxidized into Cr(VI). Two moles of KClO_4 and 8/3 moles of KClO_3 are required for the complete oxidation of a mole of Cr_2O_3 into $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. The present investigation deals with the thermal decomposition of different molar ratios of KClO_4 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and KClO_3 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The studies are followed by thermogravimetry and differential thermal analysis and the decomposition products are characterized by chemical analysis, infrared spectral measurements and X-ray powder diffraction patterns. The aim of the study was two fold. The first is to find out the influence of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the decomposition of KClO_4 and KClO_3 and the second is to estimate the extent of oxidation of Cr(III) by the oxidants.

Experimental

Materials: KClO_4 used was BDH (London) and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was Baker analyzed reagent. Commercially available KClO_3 was recrystallized and used. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade quality.

Methods: Mixtures of KClO_4 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and KClO_3 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared in 1 : 2, 1 : 1, 2 : 1, 3 : 1, 4 : 1 and 8 : 1 molar ratios by taking the required amounts and grinding in an agate mortar.

The thermogravimetric studies were made in air using a Stanton recording thermobalance at a heating rate of 6° per min., with about 100 mg samples in platinum crucible containers. Differential thermal analyses

were made on a Netzsch differential thermal analyzer using inert alumina as reference material. About 70-100 mg samples were taken for each run and the heating rate of the furnace was kept at 10° per min. Muffle furnace was employed to heat the reaction mixtures to a particular temperature in order to get the desired products for further characterization.

Infrared spectra were recorded in the range 1400-200 cm^{-1} with a Beckman IR 12 spectrophotometer using KBr pellet and nujol mull techniques.

X-ray powder photographs were taken with a Philips X-ray generator using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ -radiation and 11 46 cm Debye-Scherrer camera.

Analytical: Cr(VI) and Chloride contents were determined by the standard methods⁵. Cr(VI) in CrO_2Cl_2 was determined as follows: The different molar ratios of the mixtures were taken in an all-glass apparatus and were heated slowly from room temperature to 400°. The gaseous products evolved were trapped in a flask containing water. Chromyl chloride formed during the decomposition gets hydrolysed and the solution was boiled to expel out the dissolved chlorine. Cr(VI) in the solution was determined by iodometric method.

Results and Discussion

Potassium perchlorate and chromium (III) chloride system: The thermogravimetric and DTA plots of 1 : 2, 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 4 : 1 molar ratios of KClO_4 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are given in Fig. 1 and the plots of 3 : 1 and 8 : 1 were similar to those of 4 : 1. The TG curves indicate that the mass loss occurs at different temperature ranges. The first stage of decomposition occurs between 100°-220°, and the second stage takes place in the temperature range 300°-450°. Molar ratios 2 : 1 and higher exhibit a third stage between 420°-500°.

Free KClO_4 starts decomposing around 590° after a phase transformation² at 300° . Preliminary experiments on the thermal decomposition of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suggested that it starts dehydrating at 100° and gives Cr_2O_3 at 400° . There is no clear indication of the formation of anhydrous chromium chloride.

The infrared spectra of the residues of the mixtures 2 : 1, 3 : 1, 4 : 1 and 8 : 1 are quite similar and had adsorptions at (cm^{-1}) 1303w, 950s, 905s, 890s, 798s, 760s, 565m, 420w and 375m. These values corresponded^{6,7} to those of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. On the other hand, the spectra of the residues of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios

Fig. 1. TG and DTA plots of 4:1 (A), 2:1 (B), 1:1 (C) and 1:2 (D) molar ratios of KClO_4 and $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The different molar mixtures are heated in a muffle furnace to 500° and the products are analyzed. CrO_2Cl_2 formed during the decomposition was also analysed for Cr(VI) content by heating the mixtures to 400° and collecting the gas in an all-glass apparatus. The analytical data are given in Table 1. The results suggest that Cr(III) is completely oxidized into Cr(VI), when the molar ratios of KClO_4 to $\text{CrCO}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are 2:1 and higher.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA ON THE RESIDUES OF DECOMPOSITION OF DIFFERENT MOLAR RATIOS OF KClO_4 AND $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Molar ratio KClO_4 : $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Chromium (VI) (%) in		Extent of Cr(III) Oxidation (%)	Chloride (%)
	$\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$	CrO_2Cl_2		
1 : 1	5.89	5.71	74.9	1.46
1 : 1	9.10	4.20	89.0	2.35
2 : 1	7.38	2.32	100	8.21
3 : 1	6.69	0.93	99.9	10.8
4 : 1	5.48	0.82	99.3	13.4
8 : 1	3.30	0.47	99.5	18.3

exhibited infrared bands due to $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and additional frequencies at (cm^{-1}) 620s, 558m and 400w, which are characteristic⁸ of Cr_2O_3 .

Further confirmation of the products of decomposition was achieved by X-ray powder photography. The X-ray patterns of the decomposition residues of 2 : 1, 3 : 1, 4 : 1 and 8 : 1 molar ratios are identical with major lines at (\AA) 3.65m, 3.42m, 3.29s, 3.01s, 2.85s, 2.58w, 2.01w characteristic⁹ of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and lines at (\AA) 3.71s, 2.18m and 1.80m due to KCl. The d-spacings of the residues of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios showed lines due to $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ and KCl in addition to characteristic lines of Cr_2O_3 ⁹ at (\AA) 2.68m, 2.49s, 1.66s.

The decomposition products of various mixtures obtained around 300° were characterized and found to be the mixture of KClO_4 and Cr_2O_3 . A part of chromium chloride is also oxidized into CrO_2Cl_2 . The DTA peaks observed around 70° and 140° are assigned to melting and dehydration of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The endothermic peak at 300° is due to the phase transformation of KClO_4 and that at 400° is due to the melting of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. The exothermic peak around 270° is ascribed to the formation of CrO_2Cl_2 and that around

350° is due to the formation of $K_2Cr_2O_7$. In the molar ratios higher than 2 : 1, exothermic peak exhibited around 450° is due to the decomposition of unreacted $KClO_4$.

Potassium chlorate chromium (III) chloride system :

The TG and DTA plots of 1 : 2, 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 4 : 1 molar ratios are given in Fig 2. The molar ratios 3 : 1 and 8 : 1 behave similar to that of 8 : 1 and their curves are not included. The mass loss curves suggest that the decomposition takes place in two steps. The first stage occurs in the temperature range 100-220° and the second stage takes place between 280°-400°. Similar to the system, $KClO_4$ - $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, various molar ratios are heated in a muffle furnace and the residues are analyzed for Cr(VI) and Cl^- contents. Cr(VI) in CrO_2Cl_2 formed is also determined and the analytical results are tabulated in Table 2. It is clear from Table 2 that Cr(III) is completely oxidized into Cr(VI) when the molar ratios are three and higher. The products of decomposition are further examined by infrared spectra and X-ray powder patterns. The results confirmed that the residues of 1 : 2, 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratios are the mixture of $K_2Cr_2O_7$, KCl and Cr_2O_3 , whereas those of 3 : 1, 4 : 1 and 8 : 1 are the mixture of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and KCl.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA ON THE DECOMPOSITION PRODUCTS OF DIFFERENT MOLAR RATIOS OF $KClO_4$ AND $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$.

Molar ratio $KClO_4$: $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$	Chromium (VI) (%) in		Extent of Cr(III) Oxidation (%)	Chloride (%)
	$K_2Cr_2O_7$	CrO_2Cl_2		
1 : 2	1.23	0.79	15.9	4.52
1 : 1	2.71	1.77	33.9	7.18
2 : 1	8.01	1.09	89.5	7.81
3 : 1	7.32	0.80	98.8	11.2
4 : 1	5.62	0.60	100	12.8
8 : 1	3.91	0.31	100	19.1

The DTA curves exhibited three endothermic peaks around 70°, 140° and 400° which are assigned to the melting and dehydration of $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ and to the melting of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ respectively. The exothermic peak around 280° is ascribed to the formation of CrO_2Cl_2 and that around 360° is due to the formation of $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

Fig. 2. TG and DTA plots of 4:1 (A), 2:1 (B), 1:1 (C) and 1:2 (D) molar ratios of $KClO_4$ and $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$.

Conclusion

Potassium perchlorate and potassium chlorate chemically interact with chromium(III) chloride and get converted into $K_2Cr_2O_7$. A part of chromium is also lost in the form of CrO_2Cl_2 . However, the amount of the chromyl chloride formed decreases with the increase in amount of $KClO_4$ and $KClO_3$. This is probably due to the oxidation of chloride by the perchlorate and the chlorate.

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